

MAIN CHARACTERISTICS AND DIRECTIONS OF PRODUCTION ACTIVITY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF AN AUDIOVISUAL PROJECT

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Abstract: The article talks about the pedagogical and professional issues of preparing students for the creative production process in production activities.

Key words: production activity, creative works, expert teachers, students, media.

ОСНОВНЫЕ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ И НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ПРИ РАЗРАБОТКЕ АУДИОВИЗУАЛЬНОГО ПРОЕКТА

Аннотация: В статье говорится о педагогических и профессиональных вопросах подготовки студентов к творческому процессу производственной деятельности.

Ключевые слова: производственная деятельность, творческие работы, преподаватели-эксперты, студенты, средства массовой информации.

INTRODUCTION

Production activity and its pedagogy with its creative and organizational features are fundamentally different from other areas of art education. Because, in this process, the student's creative thinking, coming up with new ideas, and knowing the needs of consumers for the creative product they want to produce are in the first place. In the field, pedagogues teach students the content and essence of creative works and aspects of creative production both theoretically and practically. Of course, we cannot say that it is perfectly taught. Because, in order to master production skills, the student needs special professional diligence and love for the field. At the same time, special professional skills and abilities are required from pedagogues. A teacher who has studied the subject of dramatist, culture and arts management, and the skills of organizing cultural events cannot pass this subject. In order to teach this subject to students, a teacher must have creative production skills. In addition, he should have practical and professional skills in creative fields such as television, cinematography, show business. Especially in today's fast and information age, trends in the field of culture and art are changing frequently, new modern professions are emerging day by day, and these pedagogues are tasked with new systematic work.

MAIN PART

First of all, the issue of enrolling students in production education requires a unique approach. It is advisable for the applicant who wants to enter this field of study to pass the exam in three stages.

❖ The first stage is the interview stage. At this stage, the applicant will watch (promote) pre-registered movies, TV shows, concerts and other creative projects. During the interview, he will have to analyze the projects he has seen.

❖ The second step is the design phase. At this stage, the applicant must design a specific idea and show in writing the stages of turning it into a product.

❖ The third stage is the imagination stage. At this stage, the applicant chooses a topic and writes a story on that topic.

I believe that the above stages of admission will create a suitable basis for the training of high-quality personnel.

When introducing students to the field, it is necessary to pass the lessons through interesting practical and professional training. In higher education institutions abroad, specialists in theater, cinema or live broadcasts are invited to teach in all aspects of the media through extensive training. This internship allows students to learn new skills and experiences. In the field of production, students can develop in-depth knowledge, understanding and experience of their specialization over 4 years, allowing students to enter directly into arts-related employment after graduation.

In Uzbekistan, one of the production is seen in "carrying the singer around". "Partners" announce themselves as "producers" and work using the artist's entire repertoire. They dress up a boy or girl with a sweet voice and take them to weddings and "make a living". This leads to limiting the possibilities of the production industry and the singer (artist). It is advisable to approach this field from a professional point of view.

In theaters, the duties of the producer are mainly performed by the theater administrator. He mainly deals with ticket distribution, audience gathering, hall filling. Finding funds is carried out on the basis of legal regulations established by the theater management. The main goal of the administrator is to constantly provide the theater with viewers, and they do not care about repertoire, acting, directing. This situation cannot be called production. Because the producer chooses a resource that is focused on a specific goal, improves it and prepares it for "marketing". And the market needs only quality products. That's why he goes on the path of self-recovery and "profit" by providing financial support for staging the play, preparing scenery, costumes and masks, props and props [1].

At the stage of development of an audiovisual project, in addition to appointing a screenwriter, the director together with the producer will develop and give the creative task to the composer, the main task will be to create a collection of multi-genre musical themes at the same time with a common similarity and reflects the character, the mood of the main characters and the actions that take place in the frame. More importantly, the developer of the work must carry out a series of legal procedures to "clear the rights", that is, to enter into agreements with the copyright holders for the commercial use of the objects, copyright and related rights and other basic obligations and includes powers. Such contracts can consist of various periods of film production, from direct assembly to the end of the comprehensive period.

President Sh. Mirziyoyev: We all know what complex tasks are set before us by today's intense times.

In order to solve them and achieve our noble goals, to be globally competitive, we need to arm our people, first of all, our youth with science, enlightenment and spirituality, and the achievements of development. Today, we should continue the great work we have started on raising the higher education system to a new level of quality, eliminating the existing problems in the field, and turning our universities into major centers of education and science [2] - he said.

To improve and fundamentally improve the level and quality of training of highly qualified specialists who meet the growing intellectual, aesthetic and cultural needs of our people in the field of culture and art in the field of theater, cinema, television, music, folk art in our republic, as well as this Expanding the capabilities of the existing material and technical bases created in the

higher educational institutions of the field has a great impact on the further development of this field. By uniting creative forces in the field of art and culture, creating a great creative environment and creating a great creative process, further raising the level of art and culture, and of course, spreading and glorifying the art and culture of Uzbekistan to the world. - is one of the main tasks of this field[3].

As a result, specialist teachers need to learn a wide range of technical skills and training. Educators continue to learn how to implement new concepts, such as creative development and design, not only from industry experts who attend master classes themselves. The era shows that holding students to a lecture in an empty room for 80 minutes is outdated.

Now, if students in this field do not gain experience at the international level, they will continue to lag behind in educational practice. Gaining experience abroad gives the student the following opportunities.

Effective use of modern technology:

Students have access to industry-standard facilities, state-of-the-art equipment and the latest technology.

In addition to technical skills and training, he will learn parts of design and concept implementation.

When students go abroad, they will be able to adapt to different places and creative systems and will have a great experience.

A creator is a pupil or student with independent creativity. Creativity is a type of activity resulting in the creation of new material and spiritual values. The developmental function of creativity is a phenomenon that serves to carry out the educational process in an integrated manner, and includes the levels of achievement of such aspects as intellectual, sensitive and self-willed pursuit of a person [4]. The level of creative mastery is the level of learning materials that allows students to apply their knowledge and skills in different situations, to look for different ways to solve problems.

Although it has not been many years since the opening of the "Production in the field of art" educational direction at the State Institute of Arts and Culture of Uzbekistan, further improvement of the process of personnel training and their qualification, in which modern pedagogical and information Experiences on the use of technologies, advanced international experiences were studied and plans were drawn up. If work is carried out according to the plans, the expected results will be achieved. The first way to become a producer is to get a higher education in your field. A student studies for four years.

CONCLUSION

Today, the second way to get into the production profession is to complete shorter courses at media centers or to undergo professional training at film, radio or television schools. The advantage of this type of education is its quickness and training with the advice of practicing experts.

According to the analyzes of foreign producers, production is the art of creative production and management, and it becomes a direction of great importance for continuing the career of a professional artist.

In Uzbekistan, the lack of new courses and creative schools for preparing students for the creative production process has a negative impact on the development of the industry, causing an increase in amateurs.

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